

Correlation Between Depression, Anxiety and Stress with *Oral Burning Sensation* in the Elderly

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Oral burning sensation* (OBS) is a burning or stinging sensation in the mucosa, lips and/or tongue. This condition is most often associated with burning mouth syndrome (BMS). BMS has been associated with psychogenic factors such as depression, anxiety, and stress. As we age, there are many factors that cause depression, anxiety, and stress, which can interfere with the function of the human body. Therefore, this study wants to dig deeper into the correlation between psychological conditions and the occurrence of OBS, especially in the elderly. This research aims to determine the correlation between depression, anxiety and stress with OBS in the elderly.

Method: This cross-sectional study involved 112 elderly people who did not have comorbidities (not taking regular medication). Respondents were interviewed to fill in the questionnaire. The research questionnaire, consisting of the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21) questionnaire to measure psychological conditions, and the Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) to assess OBS experiences. The questionnaire results were further analyzed using the Mann-Whitney test to see the significance value of the correlation between each of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Results: There was no significant correlation between depression and OBS ($p=0.062$, $p>0.05$). However, there was a significant correlation between anxiety and OBS ($p=0.000$, $p<0.05$), and between stress and OBS ($p=0.001$, $p<0.05$).

Conclusion: OBS has a significant correlation with psychological conditions, especially anxiety and stress. However, in this study there was no significant correlation between depression and OBS.

KEYWORDS: Depression, stress, anxiety, elderly, oral burning sensation

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INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (WHO) has defined mental/psychological health as "a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to himself or her community." Positive psychological health is associated with optimism, purpose, gratitude, resilience, positive affect (i.e., positive emotions), and happiness. Negative psychological health includes depression, chronic stress, anxiety, anger, pessimism, and dissatisfaction with life.¹ When assessing an individual's psychological status,

many aspects of the individual can be assessed, but the most frequently looked at aspects include levels of depression, anxiety and stress. The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS) by Lovibond is one of the questionnaire-based measuring instruments that has been developed to reveal an individual's psychological status, and determine the level of negative emotional states.²

Oral burning sensation (OBS) is a burning or stinging sensation in the mucosa, lips and/or tongue that is often found with dry mouth (xerostomia). Both dry mouth and burning sensation in the oral mucosa can have various causes. Diseases of the oral mucosa that are related to

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genetics, inflammation, or neoplastic, autoimmune diseases, allergies, internal diseases, neurological and psychiatric diseases can also cause OBS. In addition to xerostomia, neurological disorders, allergies and other conditions that can be associated with OBS, this sensation is most often associated with burning mouth syndrome (BMS). Burning mouth syndrome (BMS), also known as glossopyrosis, glossodynia, oral dysaesthesia or stomatodynia, is an idiopathic condition with the main complaint of OBS without any visible mucosal lesions.³

Several factors have been associated with the cause of BMS including hormonal disorders and psychogenic factors such as anxiety, depression, and stress. Psychogenic factors such as personality and mood changes (especially anxiety and depression) have been consistently shown in patients with BMS, and have been used to suggest that BMS is a psychogenic problem. A study conducted by Pokupec-Gruden et al. cited by Kumar et al. (2020), verified that anxiety and depression were most common in patients with BMS. Amenabar et al. cited by Kumar et al. (2020), also found higher anxiety scores and salivary cortisol levels in patients with BMS compared to control subjects. According to this study, psychological disorders may be associated with BMS. Specifically, levels of anxiety, depression, somatization symptoms, and frequency of adverse events in patients with BMS were higher than in the control group (without BMS).⁴

The psychological condition of the elderly is greatly influenced by the problems experienced by the individual concerned. Problems in the lives of the elderly are manifestations of changes experienced during their lives, and also reactions to these changes that accompany the aging process. There are some elderly who can adapt very well, but there are also some elderly who cannot overcome problems and changes because they are unable and not ready to face their old age. Increased emotional tendencies in the elderly can cause problems from changes that cannot be overcome by them, resulting in the emergence of mental health disorders including anxiety, stress and depression. In general, there are several forms of problems that exist in old age, including problems with work, interests, loneliness, disinhibition, mood, and faith.⁵

According to Darmono as quoted by Puspawati (2017), the prevalence value of depression in the elderly undergoing treatment in hospitals and nursing homes is 30-45%. Meanwhile, according to Frazer, Christensen & Griffith as quoted by Puspawati (2017), the prevalence value of depression in community units is more varied, ranging from 1-35%. Deruma and Sato as quoted by Puspawati (2017) stated that there is a relationship between depression, lifestyle, and quality of life in the elderly. Deruma and Sato conducted a study by comparing depression, lifestyle, and quality of life, and found that elderly women who are very old are more susceptible to depression and decreased quality of life. Click or tap here to enter text.⁶

Several studies have found a relationship between depression, anxiety and stress in the elderly and OBS, however, there are also a number of studies that have not found a relationship between the two factors. In addition, there is also a relationship between the elderly and negative psychological conditions, and also between the elderly and OBS complaints, which have not been widely studied. Click or tap here to enter text.⁷ As people age, many changes occur, such as the elderly losing their jobs, the risk of developing diseases, loneliness, and so on. Older adults appear to be less able to cope with stress, an effect thought to be related to negative changes in an individual's life related to their age. Major depression has been found in 20-25% of elderly patients with medical illnesses, so the incidence of depression and suicide increases significantly after the age of 65.⁸ Meanwhile, Suga et al. (2018) estimated that the prevalence rate of OBS would increase from 1% to 3.7% in the aging population. This study also found that the proportion of BMS patients increased gradually with age at the psychosomatic-dental clinic at Tokyo University of Dentistry.⁷

This study aims to determine the correlation between individual psychological conditions including depression, anxiety and stress, with OBS in the elderly.

METHOD

This observational-analytic correlation study aims to see the relationship between a phenomenon and another phenomenon using a correlation test or correlation coefficient. The design of this study is cross-sectional *cross-sectional* and associative hypothesis to explain the relationship between depression, anxiety and stress in the elderly and oral burning sensation (OBS) in the elderly. Research in the form of a questionnaire for the elderly population at the Budi Mulia 4 Jakarta Social Welfare Home. The sampling technique in this study was purposive sampling. The sample size was determined by the sample size calculation formula with the Slovin formula and a deviation value of 0.05. The number of research subjects was 112 with inclusion criteria of healthy elderly or those with comorbidities that have been controlled and do not take medication regularly.

Before data collection, the researcher's biodata sheet, information sheet and informed consent sheet will be read to the subject, then the research subject must sign and include their full name on the informed consent sheet to state their agreement to participate in the research. Data collection will be carried out by filling out a research questionnaire consisting of two parts, namely the DASS-21 questionnaire to measure psychological conditions, and the NRS to assess the OBS experience of the research subject. The DASS-21 questionnaire consists of 3 subscales, namely the depression, anxiety and stress subscales, where each subscale consists of 7 items. There are four answer choices provided for each statement, namely 0 (never), 1 (sometimes), 2 (quite often),

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or 3 (very often). The research team can put a cross (X) in one of the columns that best suits the subject's experience over the past six months. Meanwhile, the section on oral burning sensation (OBS) consists of a numeric rating scale (NRS) assessment of the quality of OBS experienced by the research subject. The NRS is the most widely used instrument for pain screening (Figure 1). Interpretation of NRS results is adjusted to the criteria for categorizing individual pain experiences,

including none (0), mild (1–3), moderate (4–6), and severe (7–10). NRS has been studied extensively in research with adults. Because the research subjects in this study are elderly, data collection in the form of questionnaires will be assisted by the researcher to prevent and minimize obstacles that may be experienced by respondents. The researcher will provide a team to help research subjects fill out the questionnaires that are available for research.

Figure 1. Numeric Rating Scale (NRS)

The data analysis of this study will be carried out with the help of the Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS) program. This program is used to conduct the Pearson Chi-Square test to find out whether there is a significant correlation between the three independent variables (depression, anxiety and stress), which will be tested individually against the dependent variable (OBS). In the Pearson Chi-Square test, the value that will be seen is the expected count value. If the number of expected counts does not meet the requirements of the Pearson Chi-Square test (expected count > 5 more than 20%), then the alternative test that will be used is the Mann-Whitney test. The final value, namely the p-value of the correlation test, will be compared with the significance value (alpha), which is 0.05. If $p < 0.05$, it can be concluded that there is a significant association between the two variables.

This research has received a certificate of ethical clearance from the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo University (Beragama) number 39/KEPK/FKGUPDMB/IV/2022.

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

The subjects in this study were the elderly from the Budi Mulia 4 Tresna Werdha Social Home, whose ages ranged between 60 and 100 years. The results showed that there were 112 research subjects, consisting of 49 men (43.8%) and 63 women (56.3%). Ages ranged from a minimum value of 60 years, and a maximum value of 100 years with an average age of 68.61 years.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Number of Subjects Based on Age (n=112)

	Respondent Age
Average (Mean)	68.61
Standard Deviation (SD)	8,062
Median	66
Mode	60
Range	40
Minimum	60
Maximum	100

Furthermore, the results of the DASS-21 questionnaire filled out by respondents provide an overview of the experience of depression, anxiety and stress in the research subjects and the NRS questionnaire provides an

overview of the experience of Oral Burning Sensation (OBS). The subjects' experiences related to these conditions can be detailed as follows:

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Number of Subjects Based on Experience of Depression, Anxiety and Stress (n=112)

Depression Experience	n	%
Depression	39	34.8
Not Depressed	73	65.2

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Total	112	100
Anxiety Experience	n	%
Anxiety	34	30.4
No Anxiety	78	69.6
Total	112	100
Stress Experience	n	%
Stres	22	19.6
No Stress	90	80.4
Total	112	100

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Number of Subjects Based on Oral Burning Sensation (OBS) Experience (n=112)

OBS Experience	n	%
Never/ Not Sick	82	73.2
Light	18	16.1
Currently	8	7.1
Heavy	4	3.6
Total	112	100

Inferential Analysis

The association or difference between the independent variables (experience of depression, anxiety and stress) and the dependent variable (OBS experience) was tested using the Mann-Whitney test. The following tables

illustrate the association of depression, anxiety and stress conditions in the elderly and OBS experience. The value referred to is the p-value, namely If $p < 0.05$, then there is a significant association. The results of the analysis in more detail are as follows:

Table 3. Differences in Oral Burning Sensation Experience Based on Depression Experience Variables

Oral Burning Sensation Experience	Depression Experience		Total
	Depression	Not Depressed	
Never/ Not Sick	25 (30.5%)	57 (69.5%)	82
Light	6 (33.3%)	12 (66.7%)	18
Currently	5 (62.5%)	3 (37.5%)	8
Heavy	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	4
Total	39	73	112

Table 4. Conclusions from the Mann-Whitney Test on the Relationship between Depression Experience and Oral Burning Sensation Experience

Null Hypothesis (H0)	Test	Sig. (p-value)
There is no correlation between depression and oral burning sensation (OBS) in the elderly.	<i>Independent samples</i> -Mann-Whitney test	0.062

*The p-value for the Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.05$ indicates that there is a significant association between the two variables.

Table 5. Differences in Oral Burning Sensation Experience Based on Anxiety Experience Variables.

Oral Burning Sensation Experience	Anxiety Experience		Total
	Anxiety	No Anxiety	
Never/ Not Sick	16 (19.5%)	66 (80.5%)	82
Light	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	18
Currently	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	8
Heavy	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	4
Total	34	78	112

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Table 6. Conclusions from the Mann-Whitney Test on the Relationship between Anxiety Experience and Oral Burning Sensation Experience.

Null Hypothesis (H0)	Test	Sig. (p-value)
There is no correlation between anxiety and oral burning sensation (OBS) in the elderly.	<i>Independent samples</i> -Mann-Whitney test	0,000*

*The p-value for the Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.05$ indicates that there is a significant association between the two variables.

Table 7. Differences in Oral Burning Sensation Experience Based on Stress Experience Variables.

Oral Burning Sensation Experience	Stress Experience		Total
	Stres	No Stress	
Never/ Not Sick	11 (13.4%)	71 (86.6%)	82
Light	3 (16.7%)	15 (83.3%)	18
Currently	5 (62.5%)	3 (37.5%)	8
Heavy	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	4
Total	22	90	112

Table 8. Conclusions from the Mann-Whitney Test on the Relationship between Anxiety Experience and Oral Burning Sensation Experience

Null Hypothesis (H0)	Test	Sig. (p-value)
There is no correlation between stress and oral burning sensation (OBS) in the elderly.	<i>Independent samples</i> -Mann-Whitney test	0.001*

*The p-value for the Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.05$ indicates that there is a significant association between the two variables.

The results of the Mann-Whitney test in table 4 show the asymp. Sig. (2 tailed) or p-value of 0.062, it can be concluded that there is no significant correlation between depression experiences and OBS experiences in the elderly. Table 6 shows the asymp. Sig. (2 tailed) or p-value of 0.000, it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between anxiety experiences and OBS experiences in the elderly. Table 8 shows the asymp. Sig. (2 tailed) or p-value of 0.001. The p value < 0.05 , it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between stress experiences and OBS experiences in the elderly.

DISCUSSION

The frequency distribution of the number of research subjects based on depression experience shows that there are more respondents who do not experience depression than respondents who do, with a ratio of 65.2% to 34.8%. Compared to similar studies such as Rezazadeh et al. (2021), the proportion of depression experience found does not match the results of this study. The majority of subjects in Rezazadeh et al.'s study (2021), 63.2% experienced depression, while the remaining 32.8% did not experience depression.⁹For the elderly in Indonesia, Novayanti et al. (2020) stated that the highest level of depression was in the elderly who lived in social institutions, with a percentage of mild depression of 40.7%.¹⁰Saraswati et al. (2019) also found that the results of their study showed that 6.7% of elderly

people who attended the Denpasar community welfare association suffered from mild depression.¹¹ Although there are a number of studies that do not agree with the findings of the proportion of depressive experiences, a study by Braud et al. (2016) on the relationship between idiopathic BMS and quality of life stated that in their study, 66.7% of respondents did not experience depression.¹²

The frequency distribution of the number of research subjects based on anxiety experience shows that there are more respondents who do not experience anxiety than respondents who experience anxiety, with a ratio of 69.6% to 30.4%. Rezazadeh et al.'s (2021) study found that the majority of subjects in their study, 57.9%, experienced anxiety, while the remaining 42.1% did not experience anxiety.⁹ This high percentage can be attributed to several national statistical findings based on Indonesian Health Research Data, which states that mental disorders such as anxiety and depression showed a prevalence of 6% in 2013.¹³ Meanwhile, in the United States, the lifetime prevalence of anxiety disorders is more than 25%.¹ Although there are a number of sources that disagree with the findings of this study's proportion of anxiety experiences, a study by Braud et al. (2016) regarding the relationship between idiopathic BMS and quality of life stated that in his study, 61.2% of respondents did not experience anxiety.¹²

The frequency distribution of the number of research subjects based on stress experience shows a large difference

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between the number of respondents who did not experience stress compared to respondents who did. The results showed that there were more subjects who did not experience stress than subjects who did, with a ratio of 80.4% to 19.6%. This proportion is different from a similar study by Rezazadeh et al. (2021), which stated that the majority of subjects in the study, 63.2%, experienced stress, while the rest (32.8%) did not experience stress.⁹In addition, Pujar & Badami (2022) also found that only 20% of their research subjects did not experience stress, and the rest experienced moderate (17.5%) to severe (62.5%) stress.¹⁴Varghese et al.(2020)also found that only 23.3% of his research subjects fell into the no stress/mild stress group, while the others experienced moderate (46.7%) to severe (30%) stress.¹⁵Santoso & Tjihh (2021) found that the prevalence of stress in elderly people in social institutions (30%) was higher than in elderly people living with their families (8.34%). Elderly people living in nursing homes tend to experience severe stress, while elderly people living with their families tend to experience mild stress.¹⁶

The results of the frequency distribution of OBS experiences in the research subjects showed that the results with the largest percentage of OBS experiences were never experiencing OBS, at 73.2%. Furthermore, followed by mild OBS experiences of 16.1%, then moderate OBS (7.1%), and severe OBS with a percentage of only 3.1%. This finding is in line with the statistical figures presented by Aravindan et al. (2014) in their research on BMS, which stated that the prevalence of OBS in BMS ranges from 0.6% to 15% on an international scale, and this value increases in elderly individuals. In accordance with the research results, the prevalence value is not a high level.¹⁷

In this study, there was no significant correlation between depression and OBS experience in the elderly. There are several studies with different results, such as Rezazadeh et al.(2021)who found that there was a significant association between depression and BMS with a p value of 0.006 ($p<0.05$), but anxiety had no relationship to the occurrence of BMS with a p value of 0.05 ($p>0.05$).⁹This statement is reinforced by research by Nagao et al.(2021) which states thatOBS symptoms were shown to improve after administration of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and benzodiazepines, which are drugs used to treat comorbid depression. This suggests that BMS may be directly related to depression severity, which is thought to be because depression and pain share similar biological pathways.¹⁸ The difference in results between this study and other similar studies may be due to selection and sample size that is less able to describe the entire population.¹⁹

There is a significant correlation between anxiety and OBS experience in the elderly in this study. This finding is in accordance with the results of Putri et al.'s (2018) study which stated that there is a significant correlation between anxiety levels and OBS.¹³Buljan et al. as cited by Putri et al.(2018),showed that there was a relationship between

anxiety and BMS with a p value <0.01 and a strong correlation between the level of anxiety and the severity of BMS.¹³Malta et al.(2021)found that psychological factors were directly related to BMS, and anxiety was the most influential variable.²⁰ Goubert et al. cited by Tu et al.(2021)found that there was a significant correlation between anxiety and alertness and perception of pain. Some authors hypothesize that this phenomenon involves central sensitization. According to Smith et al. who was also cited by Tu et al.(2021), a person with high anxiety has a lower threshold for pain stimuli, so pain will appear more easily.¹⁹

There was a significant correlation between stress and OBS experience in the elderly in this study. This finding is in accordance with a similar study by Rezazadeh et al.(2021)who found that there was a significant association between stress and BMS with a p value of 0.001 ($p<0.05$). Research by Jedel et al.(2021)also found that stress levels were higher in the study group, namely women with BMS, compared to the control group.²¹ Batabyal et al.'s study.(2021)regarding the relationship between stress and cortisol levels in the body showed that the highest cortisol levels in the research subjects were at the time of assignment submission and final year exam time. This proves that cortisol levels are directly affected by stress.²²Meanwhile, Putri et al.(2018),explains that cortisol plays a role in the regeneration and protection of nerve tissue, and high cortisol levels can damage nerve tissue and stimulate neuropathic changes that can cause symptoms in BMS.¹³

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted at the Budi Mulia 4 Tresna Werdha Social Home for the elderly by giving a research questionnaire containing the DASS-21 and NRS sections related to OBS to assess the correlation between depression, anxiety and stress with OBS. The results of the analysis showed that there was a significant correlation between anxiety and OBS, and also stress and OBS. Meanwhile, for the depression variable, there was no significant correlation between depression and OBS.

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